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Social capital of rice farmers in various typologies of rice lands in south Sumatra

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Abstract

The aim of the research is to quantify the level of social capital conditions of rice farmers in 3 typologies of tidal, swamp and rainfed rice fields in South Sumatra. This research is carried out in 3 locations in South Sumatra in rural areas based on rice farmers and representing three land typologies, namely Ogan Ilir District, Pemulutan District, Tanjung Pasir Village for the Swamp land typology, Banyuasin District, Muara Telang District, Upang Jaya Village for the Tidal Land Typology, and OKI Regency, Lempuing Jaya District, Lubuk Seberuk Village for rainfed land typology. The research used the Likert scale method to analyze the state of social capital of rice farmers in Banyuasin Regency. The results of measuring farmers' social capital on Three Land Typologies in South Sumatra using a Likert scale obtained a score of 53.11 for the lowland land typology in Tanjung Pasir Village, Pemulutan District, Ogan Ilir Regency, 55.02 for the rainfed land typology in Lubuk Seberuk Village, Lempuing Jaya District, Ogan Komering Ili Regency and 59.96 for the tidal land typology in Upang Jaya Village, Muara Telang District, Banyuasin Regency, which means that farmers' social capital is included in the High criteria for these three land typologies.

Keywords: Farmers, Land Typology; Likert Scale; Rice Fields; Social Capital

1. Introduction

Development that focuses on economic growth means focusing development attention on areas that can contribute to high economic growth. National development goals include several aspects such as economic growth, equal distribution of people's income and employment opportunities, as well as conservation of potential resources. Apart from that, the main aim of regional economic development is to improve community welfare by increasing the number and types of employment opportunities for local communities (Tumangkeng, 2018). Successful development in Indonesia requires cooperation and support from various parties and the role of each sector. One sector that is expected to support economic development goals is the rural agricultural sector (Saridin, Martius, & Hasnah, 2022). This is because the agricultural sector is still the biggest supporter of Indonesia's national and economic development efforts. Even though our country has a lot of natural potential, in reality we still rely on imports from other countries for most of our food production, such as rice and other ingredients. Therefore, the agricultural sector must receive more attention because it is a livelihood for many Indonesians and this sector is also the most important food sector for society.

In its function as a food provider for the entire population of Indonesia, the agricultural sector is also still facing several problems. Rice production and consumption in several regions is still not balanced (Batubara & Rozaini, 2023). This is because the development of rice production as the main food of society is still fluctuating, while the demand for rice continues to increase in line with population growth in order to meet the food needs of the Indonesian population. Fluctuating conditions in rice production also occur in South Sumatra Province, which is one of the national rice granaries (Afriana & Batubara, 2020).

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One of the causes of fluctuations in rice production throughout the country is due to the conversion of agricultural land into permanent settlements and land conversion can also be done from agricultural land to industrial land. (Wardani, 2023). It could also be in the form of converting agricultural land from one commodity to another, such as from plantations to rice fields or vice versa and so on. It is also possible that agricultural land cannot be used as agricultural land again due to extreme climate change (Syafitri & Ikhsan Harahap, 2023).

Agricultural land in South Sumatra has the potential to become an alternative food source so it needs to be inventoried and conserved to be developed into superior local varieties (Oktavia, Hadi Darwanto, & Hartono, 2015; Sabila, 2020). In South Sumatra, wetland agroecosystems are the largest among various wetland agroecosystems (rainfields and wetlands), namely 341,892 ha or 72.65% of the available Raw Rice Area, compared to 52,912 Ha of rainfed rice fields which is 11.24%. The swamp land agroecosystem includes 127,438 Ha of Lebak swamp land (27.08%) and 214,454 Ha of tidal swamp land (45.57%), which currently in several areas tends to be planted with specific local varieties of rice (Badan Pusat Statistik, 2022).

In South Sumatra, rainfed rice fields cover an area of 111,758 ha, half of which is located in OKI Regency with an area of 50,570 ha. Lempuing Jaya District has rain-fed rice fields with an area of 11,412 ha, of which 1,265 ha is in Lubuk Seberuk Village. BPS data shows that the area of rain-fed rice fields in the district has decreased sharply since 2011 due to land conversion. This may be due to increased competition for land use due to the implementation of regional autonomy in the late 1990s. One of the areas experiencing a lot of conversion is Lempuing Jaya District, which experienced a decrease in land area from 19,898 hectares in 2011 (Badan Pusat Statistik, 2017).

Banyuasin Regency has the largest tidal rice fields in South Sumatra. Statistical data shows that the area of tidal rice fields in Banyuasin Regency in 2020 was 148,658 ha, of which IP 100 was 90,151 Ha, IP 200 was 58,007 Ha, and IP 300 was 36 Ha out of a total area of 213,813 ha. If we compare the data on the area of tidal rice fields in Banyuasin Regency in 2020 with the data for 2010, which was 172,671 hectares, then there has been a conversion of 24,013 hectares of rice fields in the last 10 years (Badan Pusat Statistik, 2022).

Land typology can influence the productivity that will be produced (Chuzaimah, Noprianto, Lastinawati, & Febriyansyah, 2016). Therefore, it is necessary to strengthen rural areas so that they can develop. Efforts to develop agricultural communities occur through changes in the structure of the agricultural economy and also through changes in the structure and patterns of social behavior of society. Social capital is an important element that can open networks between agricultural actors and other parties with an interest in agricultural activities and agricultural products, including private institutions and government institutions (Ernanda, Burhanuddin, & Purwono, 2019). Trading and marketing of agricultural products often does not provide sufficient benefits for farmers, therefore the role of social capital between agricultural actors is very important to increase the bargaining position of agricultural actors (Dumasari, Budiningsih, Darmawan, & Santosa, 2019).

Social capital plays a role in efforts to manage natural resources. Social capital plays an important role in maintaining and building social integration and also becomes a social glue in society (Wuysang, 2014). Research on social capital in the context of farmer group activities has not been widely studied. By building social capital among farmer groups, farmer groups can form networks, increase rural business activities in their area, and increase family welfare and income (Fadhila, Astutik, & Nurhadi, 2023; Fadli, 2015). Therefore, it is necessary to carry out further analysis regarding the social capital capacity of rice farmers in South Sumatra.

2. Research Methods

The research was carried out in 3 locations in South Sumatra in rural areas which are the basis for rice farmers and represent three land typologies, namely Ogan Ilir (OI) Regency, Pemulutan District, Tanjung Pasir Village with the Lebak land typology, Banyuasin Regency, Muara Telang District, Upang Jaya Village with the land typology. Tides, and OKI Regency, Lempuing Jaya District, Lubuk Seberuk Village with Rain-Fed Land Typology. The three research locations were chosen purposively based on the criteria that the three locations represent areas of each land typology in South Sumatra. This area also has a relatively large rice field area, making it a food storage area for South Sumatra. The method used in this research is a survey method. This method uses questionnaires as a tool to collect primary data from respondents and interviews with respondents including key informants as a tool to investigate the research location and identify existing facts and symptoms. This is done directly by identifying and obtaining factual information. The sampling method used was stratified random sampling using 3 layers (Masri & Nuraini Wahyuning Prasadjo, 2021). Where at each location 45 samples were taken as research respondents.

Data is measured using three indicators, namely norms, trust and networks. Each of the three indicators consists of five questions. Each question is given a value of 1 for very low criteria, a value of 2 for low criteria, a value of 3 for medium criteria, a value of 4 for high criteria, and a value of 5 for very high criteria. The questions for each indicator are arranged in the following table:

Table 1 Description of Social Capital Indicators

Description
Norm
Obey the rules that apply in the village
Comply with the contract when borrowing (capital and goods)
Pay land and building taxes
Participate in mutual cooperation activities if there are problems in farming
Pay loan money on time
Trust
Lend each other's equipment to fellow farmers
Trust the management and fellow members
Mutual support in every activity between the chairman and members
Trust the information provided by the instructor
Ask for and give advice to fellow farmers
Network
Join a farmer group
Participate (energy, time and materials) in activities in the village
Exchange information about rice
Active in conveying aspirations, suggestions, opinions
Participate in meetings to discuss farming

Respondents' answers were categorized into class intervals using the formula:

$$NR = NST - NSR \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

$$PI = NR : JIK \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Where NR is the range value, NST is the highest score value, NSR is the lowest score value, PI is the length of the interval, and JIK is the number of class intervals. Based on the results of this processing, the class intervals and criteria in the table are as follows:

Table 2 Class Intervals and Criteria for Farmers' Social Capital

Class Interval Score (Total Score)	Class Score (Per Indicator)	Class Interval Score (Per Question)	Criteria
15,0 ≤ x ≤ 27,0	5,0 ≤ x ≤ 9,0	1,00 ≤ x ≤ 1,8	Very Low
27,0 < x ≤ 39,0	9,0 < x ≤ 13,0	1,8 < x ≤ 2,6	Low
39,0 < x ≤ 51,0	13,0 < x ≤ 17,0	2,6 < x ≤ 3,4	Moderate

$51,0 < x \leq 63,0$	$17,0 < x \leq 21,0$	$3,4 < x \leq 4,2$	High
$63,0 < x \leq 75,0$	$21,0 < x \leq 25,0$	$4,2 < x \leq 5,0$	Very High

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Characteristics of Respondent Farmers

Respondent characteristics are a description of the profile or identity of farmer respondents (Suharyani, Dolorosa, & Permatasari, 2023). Respondents in this study were members of farmer groups engaged in rice cultivation in the villages of Upang Jaya (tidal rice fields), Lubuk Seberuk (rain-fed rice fields), and Tanjung Pasir (lebak rice fields). The characteristics of the respondents in this study consisted of age, gender, length of farming, education level and area of farming cultivation.

Almost all of the respondent farmers in the three villages fall into the labor force or productive age group. Based on the Central Statistics Agency, the population included in the labor force is aged 18 – 64 years. The highest age frequency among respondent farmers was in the age category 41 - 64 years for the rainfed land typology area 60.00% and lowland swamp 73.33 percent and 18 - 40 years old for the tidal land typology area 46.67 percent. The lowest age frequency of farmers is in the category above 64 years, with a total of 6 people in the three land typologies, meaning that this age group is classified as unproductive.

The level of education is an important factor in determining farmer progress and influences behavior (Darmawan, Gayatri, & Satmoko, 2021). The education level of farmers in the three land typologies is dominated by elementary school graduates, namely 57.78 percent in the lowland and tidal swamp land typology and 44.44 percent in the rainfed land typology, then the education level with the fewest respondents is more than school education. Upper Middle School such as Diploma or Bachelor's degrees, namely 4.44 percent in the lowland swamp land typology, 2.22 percent in the tidal and rainfed land typology.

More than half of the respondents in the three land typologies have cultivated rice for more than 20 years, namely 79 people. The longest time farmers have been cultivating rice on the three land typologies is more than 20 years, which proves that rice farming has been carried out on the three land typologies for a long time and has been passed down from generations to generations. The land area owned by respondent farmers ranges from 1 to 2 hectares. Farmers' land area is divided into four groups. There were 31 respondents with an area of less than 1.00 hectares of land in the three land typologies. Then, the land area of 1 to 2 hectares is 94 people in the three land typologies and the land area of more than 2 hectares is 10 people.

3.2. Conditions of Rice Farmers' Social Capital Levels

Social capital is built by a sense of mutual trust, proactive actions in internal-external relations in building social networks supported by a benevolent spirit for mutual benefit as a reflection of the strength of society (Risnawati, Rianse, & Hamzah, 2024). The measurement of social capital of rice farmers in three typologies of lowland swamp land in Ogan Ilir Regency, rainfed land in Ogan Komering Ilir Regency, and tidal land in Banyuasin Regency was measured based on assessment answers from farmers. Rice farmers' social capital is measured using three indicators, namely village norms, trust between farmers, and farmer networks.

Based on measuring indicators of farmers' social capital on three typologies of rain-fed land in Lubuk Seberuk Village, Lempuing Jaya District, Ogan Komering Ilir Regency, lowland swamp land in Tanjung Pasir Village, Pemulutan District, Ogan Ilir Regency, and tidal land in Upang Jaya Village, Muara Telang District, Banyuasin Regency, the three land typologies obtained a total score above 51, namely 52.11 for the lowland swamp land typology; 55.02 for the rain-fed land typology and 59.96 for the tidal land typology, meaning that the social capital of farmers in the three land typologies in South Sumatra is within the high criteria. This is enough to prove that the social capital of rice farmers in the three land typologies plays a role in bringing about good changes in rice farming. In Table 3, it can be seen the value of the social capital score of rice farmers and its measurement components in the three typologies of wetland, rainfed and tidal swamp land in the villages of Tanjung Pasir, Lubuk Seberuk and Upang Jaya.

Of the three criteria, namely social capital, namely the norms that exist in the three typologies of rainfed, lowland swamp land and tidal land, only the lowland swamp land typology has a moderate number of criteria scores. Meanwhile, the norm indicators for tidal and rain-fed land typologies as well as indicators of farmer trust and participation in each land typology in each village are at high criteria. In measuring the existing norms in Tanjung Pasir village with the lowland

swamp land typology, it is included in the medium criteria. The indicators of norms in the village are obeying the rules that apply in the village, obeying contracts when borrowing, paying land and building taxes, participating in mutual cooperation activities if there are problems in farming, and paying loan money on time. This shows that farmer respondents in Tanjung Pasir village have not followed the norms in that village. After cross checking with village heads, there were still many farmers who did not pay their loans on time and did not pay land and building taxes.

Table 3 Conditions of Rice Farmers' Social Capital Levels

Land Typology	Measurement Components	Question Indicator					Score	Criteria
		1	2	3	4	5		
Lebak Swamp	Norm	3.16	3.33	3.13	3.33	3.18	16.13	Moderate
	Trust	3.60	3.69	3.71	3.82	3.80	18.62	High
	Network	3.84	3.73	3.53	3.69	3.56	18.36	High
	Total						53.11	High
Rainfed	Norm	3.42	3.29	3.49	3.56	3.33	17.09	High
	Trust	3.67	3.91	3.96	3.78	3.91	19.22	High
	Network	3.87	3.76	3.58	3.76	3.76	18.71	High
	Total						55.02	High
Tidal land	Norm	3.67	3.71	3.91	3.89	3.87	19.04	High
	Trust	3.80	4.04	4.27	4.02	4.07	20.20	High
	Network	4.16	4.27	4.11	4.11	4.07	20.71	High
	Total						59.96	High

The component measuring trust between farmers in the three land typologies in each village falls within the high criteria. This shows that farmers in the three land typologies have high trust in their fellow farmers and in other people. The indicators of trust between farmers are borrowing equipment from fellow farmers, trusting the management and fellow members, supporting each other in every activity between the chairman and members, trusting the information provided by extension workers, and asking for and giving advice to fellow farmers. All farmers have a sense of trust, so social capital will be formed well. If the trust relationship is good, the farmer network will also be good. If other farmers wanted to borrow, they lent without hesitation, and farmers helped each other without suspicion. This is a form of trust that is formed between farmers in the village.

The farmer network measurement component in the three land typologies in South Sumatra is included in the high criteria. This is in accordance with the norms and beliefs held by farmers and is at high criteria. Network indicators consist of joining a farmer group, participating (material, energy and time) in village activities, sharing information about rice, actively conveying aspirations, suggestions and opinions, and participating in meetings to discuss farming. This shows that the network between farmers is good and all farming activities can run smoothly in the three typologies of wetland, tidal and rainfed rice fields.

3.3. Social Capital Measured from Norm Indicators

Norms are defined as a set of rules that must be obeyed and adhered to by members of society in a particular social unit with the aim of creating harmony. The existence of applicable norms can be relied upon to ensure order in society. Norms are measured from five research questions, namely obeying the rules that apply in the village, obeying contracts when borrowing (capital and goods), paying land and building taxes, participating in mutual cooperation activities if there are problems in farming, and paying loan money on time. Farmers' social capital measured based on applicable norms is in the medium criteria for farmers in the lowland swamp land typology with an average score of 3.23, while farmers in the other two land typologies have high criteria, namely 3.42 for the rainfed land typology and 3.81 for tidal land typology.

The first indicator measured, namely obeying all existing rules in the village, resulted in a score of 3.16 for the lowland swamp land typology, 3.42 for the rainfed land typology and 3.67 for the tidal swamp and of the three land typologies each only typology lowland swamp land with moderate criteria. Of the 135 respondents taken, only 37 rice farmers had followed the rules in the village. This shows that the village still often experiences chaos due to attempts to break the rules. Meanwhile, complying with the contract when borrowing (capital and goods) has an average score of 3.33 for the lowland swamp land typology, 3.29 for the rainfed land typology and 3.71 for the tidal land typology with the criteria for the tidal land typology being the highest of the two. other land typologies. There are still 20 percent of respondent farmers who do not comply with contracts when borrowing goods or capital at this time. 11 percent of respondent farmers are in arrears in payments from the schedule set at the beginning of the loan because the income obtained from farming results is still not sufficient for the farmer's living needs. However, there are 88.89 percent of respondent farmers who always comply with the contract when borrowing, especially on the tidal land typology.

The results of measuring the indicator of paying land and building tax is 3.13 for the lowland swamp land typology and this land typology has medium criteria, while for the rainfed land typology it is 3.49 and the tidal land typology has a score of 3.91 with high criteria. In line with the fourth norm indicator, namely paying money loans on time, it has an average score of 3.33 for the lowland swamp land typology, which means that both typologies have moderate criteria, and the tidal land typology has a score of 3.89 and 3.56 for the land typology. rain fed with high criteria. More than 50 percent of farmers in the tidal and rain-fed land typologies have complied with paying land and building taxes on time. However, in the lowland swamp land typology, as many as 20 percent of respondent farmers do not comply or do not pay taxes. Respondent farmers have often experienced crop failures in the last few years, such as floods, which have left them short of funds or do not have savings to pay land and building taxes.

The results of measurements following mutual cooperation activities if there are problems in farming have an average score of 3.18 for the lowland swamp land typology and 3.33 for the rainfed land typology with medium criteria, and 3.87 for the tidal land typology with high criteria. . The work program implemented at the research location is simultaneous planting, cleaning water channels, and making roads to rice fields. In the Lebak swamp land typology, mutual cooperation activities are rarely carried out due to the close distance between the house and the farmer's land. If problems occur in farming, farmers do it themselves without help from farmer groups. In contrast to the lowland swamp land typology, farmers in the rain-fed land typology have a long distance between their house and land, so farmers are often not in the land/rice fields when there are mutual cooperation activities and the majority of respondent farmers in this rain-fed land typology have other jobs. apart from being a farmer. Farmers in the lowland swamp and rainfed land typologies still prioritize personal interests over common interests.

3.4. Social Capital Measured by Trust Indicators

Trust is an assumption, hope, or belief that farmers will behave towards other farmers as expected and necessary to achieve good cooperation. Farmers' social capital as measured based on indicators of farmer trust is in the high criteria for the three land typologies with an average score of 3.72 for the lowland swamp land typology, 3.84 for the rainfed land typology and 4.04 for the tidal land typology, which means Trust between farmers has been built and is owned by every farmer on every land typology.

Measuring the first indicator, namely the relationship between farmers borrowing equipment from each other, resulted in an average score of 3.60 for the lowland swamp land typology, 3.67 for the rainfed land typology and 3.80 for the tidal land typology with the third criterion of the typology being high. However, when interviewed, farmers in the tidal and rain-fed land typologies rarely borrowed equipment between fellow farmers because almost all farmers already had their own tools.

Measuring the second indicator, namely trust in management and fellow members, resulted in an average score of 3.69 for the lowland swamp land typology, 3.91 for the rainfed land typology and 4.04 for the tidal land typology with the third criterion for the land typology being high. Farmers trust the management of farmer groups because the election of administrators in the villages of Tanjung Pasir and Lubuk Seberuk is held by deliberation and consensus. The form of trust that occurs in Upang Jaya Village is through collection of contributions. The money received by the management will be used to buy fertilizer. The management also trusts members that farmers will pay their debts on time.

Measurement of the third indicator, namely mutual support in each activity, produces an average score of 3.71 for the lowland swamp land typology and 3.96 for the rainfed typology with high criteria and for the tidal land typology it produces an average score of 4.27 with very high criteria. . More than 50 percent of respondent farmers support each other in every activity that occurs in each village on each land typology.

The fourth indicator measurement, namely trust in the information provided by the instructor, resulted in an average score of 3.82 for the lowland swamp land typology, 3.78 for the rainfed land typology and 4.02 for the tidal land typology with high criteria for the three land typologies. Farmers follow the information provided by extension workers regarding work methods that are more appropriate to developments, both knowledge related to cultivation methods and technology such as the use of agricultural machines or information about good fertilizer and seeds for each land typology as well as information regarding assistance from the government.

Measuring the fifth indicator, namely asking for and giving advice to fellow farmers, resulted in an average score of 3.80 for the lowland swamp land typology, 3.91 for the rainfed land typology and 4.07 for the tidal land typology with high criteria in all three typologies. land. Although in recent years meetings have been held online due to the corona virus. However, farmers continue to communicate well and continue to ask and give advice to fellow farmers.

3.5. Social Capital as Measured by Network Indicators

Networks are relationships that exist between farmers and other farmers to form groups and partnerships. Before the network between farmers was formed, each farmer already had confidence in participating in group activities. This farmer network is measured through five questions, namely joining a farmer group, participating (energy, time and materials) in activities in the village, exchanging information about rice, being active in conveying aspirations, suggestions and opinions, and finally participating in meetings to discuss farming.

Measuring the first indicator, namely joining a farmer group, resulted in an average score of 3.84 for the lowland swamp land typology, 3.87 for the rainfed land typology and 4.16 for the tidal land typology. or more than 50.00 percent of respondent farmers in each typology are in the high criteria. This means that the farmer network that is formed is the reason farmers join farmer groups of their own accord without coercion from other people.

The second indicator, namely participation (energy, time and materials) in activities in the village, has high criteria with an average score of 3.73 for the lowland swamp land typology, 3.76 for the rainfed land typology and 4.27 for the tidal land typology. . More than 50.00 percent of respondent farmers in the three land typologies were in the high category. This means that farmers in each typology play an active role in conveying opinions, energy, time and materials.

The third measurement indicator is exchanging information regarding rice which has high criteria in the typology of tidal land and lowland swamps, but in the rainfed land typology it has high criteria with an average score of 3.53, 3.58 and 4.11. In the lowland and tidal swamp land typology, meetings are held regularly in one month, twice with extension workers. If there are obstacles in carrying out farming, there are usually two meetings in one week.

The fourth indicator is actively conveying aspirations, opinions and suggestions with an average score of 3.53 for the lowland swamp land typology, 3.76 for the rainfed land typology and 4.11 for the tidal land typology or more than 60.00 percent of respondent farmers in each typology is in the high category. Farmers feel happy when they can gather with fellow farmers and convey their aspirations, suggestions and opinions.

The fifth indicator, participating in meetings to discuss farming, has an average score of 3.56 for the lowland swamp land typology, 3.76 for the rainfed land typology and 4.07 for the tidal land typology. Respondent farmers in the three land typologies often attend meetings held. If related to the meeting, more than 60 percent of the respondent farmers from the three land typologies chose to take part in the meeting which was held to discuss or find out information about rice farming.

4. Conclusion

Farmers' social capital in the Three Land Typologies in South Sumatra, namely the rainfed land typology in Lubuk Seberuk Village, Lempuing Jaya District, Ogan Komering Ilir Regency, lowland swamp land in Tanjung Pasir Village, Pemulutan District, Ogan Ilir Regency, and the tidal land typology in Upang Jaya Village, District Muara Telang, Banyuasin Regency is included in the high criteria. With this social capital, farmers are expected to be able to solve problems in all aspects in the farming environment.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of Conflict of interest

No conflicts of interest to be disclosed.

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